

Microbenthic to macrobenthic biomass responses to changes of organic matter fluxes induced by ENSO off central Peru

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The characteristics of surface sediments off Callao indicate consistently high fluxes of organic matter to the seafloor, although temporal variability is evident in association with periods of severe hypoxia and anoxia and with episodic re-oxygenation linked to La Niña (LN) and El Niño (EN) phases of ENSO, respectively. Elevated concentrations of chlorophyll-*a* in surface sediments, used here as a proxy for phytodetritus deposition, were recorded during the 2007 LN period (32.4 to 830.8 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) compared with the 2002–2003 EN period (33.5 to 66.28 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). The combined effect of high exported production and oxygen deficiency in bottom waters drives shifts in sediment redox conditions, with more reduced sediments occurring under LN conditions than during the warm ENSO phase. Increased delivery of fresh organic matter to the seafloor stimulates microbial biomass and free-living nematodes, whereas oxygen depletion negatively affects macrofaunal populations and *Thioploca* spp.

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